

Comparative Taxonomic and Morpho-Anatomical Analysis of Ayurvedic Medicinal Plants

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Manuscript details:

Received: 09.04.2026
Accepted: 09.05.2026
Published: 30.05.2026

Cite this article as:

Shivganga Anil More, Pandit BD and Patil TV (2026) Comparative Taxonomic and Morpho-Anatomical Analysis of Ayurvedic Medicinal Plants, *Int. J. of Life Sciences*, 14 (1A):145-150.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20653901>

Available online on <http://www.ijlsci.in>
ISSN: 2320-964X (Online)
ISSN: 2320-7817 (Print)

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ABSTRACT

The present study focuses on the preparation of an artificial identification key through comparative taxonomic evaluation of selected Ayurvedic medicinal plants: *Ocimum sanctum*, *Argemone mexicana*, *Justicia adhatoda* and *Vitex negundo*. The integration of macro-and micro-morphological evidence highlights the systematic importance of structural characters in medicinal plants classification. Comparative analysis of vegetative anatomical traits revealed distinct interspecific variations in epidermal organization, trichome types, vascular patterns and secretory features. These stable diagnostic characters serve as reliable markers for species identification. The findings were validated using regional taxonomic keys, enabling accurate species authentication and the development of an artificial identification key. The study emphasizes the taxonomic value of morpho-anatomical characters in strengthening systematic classification of Ayurvedic medicinal taxa.

Keywords: Ayurvedic medicinal plants, Comparative taxonomy, Taxonomic key, regional flora.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurvedic medicinal plants represent a rich reservoir of bioactive compounds and continue to function as primary healthcare resources in many parts of the world. For centuries, traditional medical systems have relied on plant-based remedies, making medicinal flora an essential component of healthcare and cultural heritage. Despite their widespread utilization, misidentification, adulteration, and substitution of medicinal species remain persistent challenges, which can compromise therapeutic efficacy and safety. These concerns highlight the urgent need for accurate taxonomic authentication of medicinal plant resources (Sharma, 1996). Taxonomy supported by morphological and anatomical evidence provides a reliable scientific framework for species authentication (Lawrence, 1951). Classical plant taxonomy has historically depended on external morphological characters such as habit, leaf arrangement, inflorescence structure, and floral organization (Bentham & Hooker, 1862-1883). However, reliance solely on gross morphology may not always resolve taxonomic ambiguities among closely related taxa exhibiting overlapping characters. Comparative structural studies are therefore essential for recognizing stable

diagnostic traits that aid in species delimitation and systematic interpretation. Anatomical investigations of vegetative organs offer additional taxonomically significant characters, including epidermal configuration, trichome diversity, vascular architecture, and secretory structures. These microstructural features are comparatively stable across environmental conditions and provide measurable, reproducible evidence for plant identification (Metcalf & Chalk, 1950; Fahn, 1990). Consequently, morpho-anatomical data are widely applied in systematic botany and pharmacognosy to strengthen classification accuracy and support the development of artificial identification keys. Regional floristic documentation further assists in validating species identity and understanding plant diversity (Gamble, 1915–1936).

Comparative investigations of medicinal plants not only advance systematic botany but also provide

scientific validation for traditional herbal knowledge (Esau, 1977). Structural analysis of medicinal taxa is therefore essential for safeguarding authenticity, ensuring therapeutic integrity, and promoting conservation of plant resources. The present study focuses on selected Ayurvedic medicinal plants belonging to diverse angiosperm families. Through comparative evaluation of morphological and anatomical characters, the study aims to identify stable diagnostic features and establish a reliable taxonomic framework for accurate authentication of medicinal species.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Four Ayurvedic medicinal plants were selected for the study: *Ocimum sanctum*, *Argemone mexicana*, *Justicia adhatoda* and *Vitex nigundo*. Fresh plant specimens were collected from local habitats and authenticated using regional floras.

Fig. 1: Geographical location of plant collection site recorded using GPS. A. *Ocimum sanctum*, B. *Argemone mexicana*, C. *Justicia adhatoda*, D. *Vitex nigundo*

Fig.2: Sequential Workflow for Comparative Anatomical Study of *Ocimum sanctum* and *Argemone mexicana*

Morphological observations were recorded from vegetative organs including leaves, stems and surface characters. For anatomical study, thin transverse sections were prepared using a sharp blade. Sections were stained with safranin and mounted in glycerin. Microscopic examination was carried out under a compound microscope to analyze epidermal patterns, trichomes, vascular bundles and secretory structures. Comparative characters were tabulated and used to prepare an artificial identification key.

RESULTS

Comparative morphological analysis revealed distinct variations in leaf morphology, venation pattern, stem characters, and external diagnostic traits among the selected Ayurvedic medicinal plants. These features served as primary taxonomic indicators. Microscopic examination of transverse sections of stem and leaf showed differences in epidermal structure, trichome type, vascular bundle arrangement, supporting tissues, and mesophyll differentiation. These stable anatomical characters proved significant for species authentication.

1. *Ocimum sanctum*

Root: Circular, single-layered epidermis; broad parenchymatous cortex; distinct endodermis; single-layered pericycle; radial vascular bundles with exarch xylem; reduced pith.

Stem: Quadrangular; single-layered cutinized epidermis; collenchymatous hypodermis; parenchymatous cortex; collateral open vascular bundles in ring; endarch xylem; large pith.

Leaf: Dorsiventral; cutinized upper epidermis; single-layered palisade; spongy mesophyll loose; collateral vascular bundles with bundle sheath; glandular trichomes present.

2. *Argemone mexicana*

Root: Multilayered cortex; prominent endodermis; radial vascular bundles with large lignified xylem; small pith.

Stem: Circular; thick epidermis; chlorenchymatous and parenchymatous cortex; ringed vascular bundles with sclerenchyma; wide pith.

Leaf: Dorsiventral; thick-walled epidermis; palisade and spongy mesophyll; laticifers present; prominent vascular bundle with lignified xylem.

3. *Justicia adhatoda*

Root: Well-developed cortex; distinct endodermis; continuous pericycle; radial exarch xylem; narrow phloem; reduced pith.

Stem: Circular; cutinized epidermis; collenchymatous cortex; collateral open vascular bundles; secondary growth; large pith.

Leaf: Dorsiventral; stomata on upper epidermis; compact palisade; loose spongy mesophyll; vascular bundle with bundle sheath; non-glandular trichomes.

Anatomical observation

Double Stained Transverse sections of Selected Medicinal Plants:

Fig. 3 (A): T.S of petiole - *Justicia adhatoda* (B) T.S of petiole - *Vitex negundo*, (C). T.S of stem - *Ocimum sanctum* (D). T.S of stem - *Vitex negundo*, (E). T.S of stem - *Argemone mexicana*.

Table 1: Morphological observation

Plant	Habit	Root	Stem	Leaf	Inflorescence	Fruit
<i>Ocimum sanctum</i>	Erect annual herb	Tap root	Quadrangular, branched	Opposite, serrate	Terminal spike	Nutlet, black
<i>Argemone mexicana</i>	Erect annual herb	Tap root	Erect, spiny	Alternate, pinnatifid, spiny	Solitary, yellow	Capsule, black
<i>Justicia adhatoda</i>	Erect shrub	Tap root	Woody, cylinder	Opposite, lanceolate, entire	Cymose	Capsule, small
<i>Vitex negundo</i>	Perennial shrub/tree	Tap root	Quadrangular, woody	Opposite, compound, digitate (5 leaflet)	Panicle	Drupe, black

Table 2: Comparative analysis

Plant species	Root anatomy	Stem anatomy	Leaf anatomy
<i>Ocimum sanctum</i>	Reduced pith, radial vascular bundles	Quadrangular stem; ringed vascular bundles	Glandular trichomes; Compact palisade mesophyll
<i>Argemone mexicana</i>	Thick cortex; lignified xylem	Sclerenchymatous patches present	Presence of laticifers
<i>Justicia adhatoda</i>	Distinct endodermis; Compact stele	Secondary growth evident	Non-glandular trichomes
<i>Vitex negundo</i>	Prominent vascular cylinder	Quadrangular outline	Abundant glandular trichomes

4. *Vitex negundo*

Root: Thick cortex; distinct endodermis; well-developed xylem; parenchymatous pith.

Stem: Quadrangular; collenchymatous hypodermis; ringed vascular bundles supported by sclerenchyma; broad pith.

Leaf: Dorsiventral; single-layered palisade; extensive spongy tissue; abundant glandular trichomes; collateral vascular bundle.

Comparative analysis:

The comparative study revealed significant interspecific variations among the selected taxa. Distinct epidermal cell arrangement and stomatal types were observed. Trichome diversity ranged from glandular to non-glandular forms. Vascular bundle organization differed in pattern and complexity, while secretory structures showed taxon-specific distribution. These stable structural traits functioned as reliable diagnostic characters. The integration of macro and micro-morphological features enabled clear differentiation of species and supported the development of an artificial identification key.

Artificial taxonomic key

1a. Stem quadrangular in transverse section; plant strongly aromatic; leaves opposite; glandular oil trichomes abundant (2)

1b. Stem terete in transverse section; plant non-aromatic; leaves alternate or opposite; oil glands absent (3)

2a. Inflorescence verticillaster; flowers bilabiate; ovary deeply four-lobed; nutlets four *Ocimum sanctum*

2b. Inflorescence not verticillaster; flowers simple actinomorphic (3)

3a. Latex exuding on injury; stem and leaves prickly; epidermis thickened with cutin; leaves pinnatifid with spiny lobes (4)

3b. Latex absent; plant unarmed; leaves simple or compound (5)

4a. Flowers large, yellow; stamens numerous; laticifers abundant in cortex and pith *Argemone mexicana*

4b. Flowers small; laticifers few (5)

5a. Leaves palmately compound, 3–5 leaflets; woody shrub; trichomes simple, non-glandular; inflorescence terminal cymose panicle *Vitex negundo*

5b. Leaves simple; herbaceous or undershrub; inflorescence dense spike; calyx tubular *Justicia adhatoda*.

DISCUSSION

Comparative morpho-anatomical analysis of selected Ayurvedic plants revealed interspecific variations supporting taxonomic delimitation and pharmacognostic authentication. Root anatomy differed in cortical thickness, vascular arrangement, and pith. *Argemone mexicana* and *Vitex negundo* showed well-developed vascular cylinders with prominent xylem, indicating mechanical strength, while *Ocimum sanctum* had reduced pith and compact vascular tissue, reflecting adaptive specialization. Stem anatomy provided diagnostic features: quadrangular stems in *Ocimum* and *Vitex* reflect collenchymatous strengthening, sclerenchymatous patches in *Argemone mexicana* add rigidity, and secondary growth in *Justicia adhatoda* indicates advanced vascular differentiation. Leaf anatomy was most informative. All species were dorsiventral, but palisade thickness, spongy mesophyll, and trichome types were species-specific. Glandular trichomes in *Ocimum sanctum*, and *Vitex negundo* relate to essential oil secretion; laticifers in *Argemone mexicana* denote phytochemical uniqueness. These anatomical markers facilitate reliable identification, reduce misidentification, and support pharmacological purity, bridging classical taxonomy and applied pharmacognosy.

CONCLUSION

Comparative morpho-anatomical characters of roots, stems, and leaves provide reliable taxonomic markers for Ayurvedic plant authentication. Species-specific anatomical traits are stable and reproducible, aiding classification, quality control, and conservation. This framework supports accurate identification, pharmacognostic validation, and systematic documentation. Future integration with phytochemical and molecular data will further enhance taxonomic clarity and medicinal reliability.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

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